

EFFECT OF WORK ENVIRONMENT ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN IBOM AIR, UYO, AKWA IBOM STATE

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Work Environment, Physical Work Environment, Psychosocial Work Environment, Technological Work Environment, Cultural Work Environment and Employee Performance.

Abstract: *Airline work environment is difficult and greatly affects performance of employees. Employee’s performance is responsible for the success of the air firm. The objective of the study was to examine the effect of work environment on employee performance in Ibom Air, Uyo. Four research questions and four null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The descriptive survey design was used for the study. The population of the study consisted of all the three hundred and three (303) staff of Ibom Air, Uyo. Multi-stage sampling procedure and simple random sampling technique were used in selecting 171 staff for the study through the application of Taro Yamene formula. Data was collected using a researcher developed instrument named, “Work Environment and Employee Performance Questionnaire (WEEQ). The instrument was further subjected to face validity by through a pilot study conducted with 30 staff in Ibom Air, Uyo who were not part of the study sample. The reliability of the instrument was determined by randomly selecting 30 staff in Ibom Air, Uyo who were not part of the study sample to respond to the instrument. Data generated was subjected to reliability test with Cronbach Alpha statistics. The instrument was considered reliable for the study as it had a reliability coefficient of 0.89. The hypotheses postulated were tested with Simple Linear Regression Statistics. The findings of the study revealed that Physical work environment, psychosocial work environment, technological work environment and cultural work environment significantly affect employee performance in Ibom Air, Uyo. Recommendations were made among others that Ibom Air management should always provide a psychosocial work environment that involves effective leadership style, work-life balance, teamwork and collaboration, and social support.*

Introduction

The industrial marketplace has been remodeled in the recent past years and has left employees to encounter many challenges that affect their performance. The issue has become an intense

competitive, unpredictable, changing, dynamic and uncertain environment that led to high inflationary to the employee performance. Human Resources are considered the key indicator of developing organizational

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performance and employee performance where the organization can easily achieve goals within their specified time (Pradhan and Jena, 2017).

There are many factors that affect the employee performance in the organization. Work environment plays an essential role towards employee performance and productivity in any organization (Elzeiny, 2015). Research shows that different countries are faced with challenges that affect employee performance. In developing countries, performance is measured by the efficiency and effectiveness of the government organs, which is heavily dependent on the performance of employees (Nigatu et al. 2017).

Employee performance declined during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, as businesses struggled to keep track of and balance the workloads of employees who worked from home and in the workplace (Wiradendi, 2020). During the shutdown in Malaysia, employees suffered mental health difficulties, which resulted in a drop in employee performance (Shan-Muhammad et al., 2020). Research further proves that in Ghana, inadequate infrastructure such as unreliable electricity supply and inadequate transportation networks, negatively impact employee performance (Yaro et al. 2021).

In Nigeria, the challenges that affect employee performance are attributed to various factors which include lack of skills and knowledge. Poor performance could be as a result of inadequate skill set and knowledge levels of employees. Many Nigerian workers lack proper training and education which hinders the ability to effectively

perform their job responsibilities (Achimugu, 2018). Nigeria has been plagued by challenges of corruption and unethical practices which in turn impacts employee performance. When employees witness or experience corruption within the organization, it can breed a culture of distrust which negatively affects their commitment and performance (Uchenna, 2019). The achievement of any organization is closely tied to the employees' performance. Magkunegara (2014) argues that employee performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. Hence, this study investigates the effect of work environment on employee performance in Ibom Air, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Statement of the Problem

The performance of the employees depends mainly on the quality of the work environment. The elements of the environment at workplace have a significant impact on the performance of the workers either towards the positive outcomes or towards the negative outcomes (Chandrasekar, 2022). Some elements of the physical work environment at the workplace can become the cause of disturbance in the performance of employees.

The employee's performance at the workplace will be dependent on the task of the job and also on the work environment factor. A good work environment will give the opportunity to employees to utilize their full energy and attention to do their job (Vischer, 2007). Hicks

(2011) opined that a poor working environment exposes employees to injuries, discomfort and helps to reduce productivity.

An organization has to provide a conducive environment that will protect them under emergency conditions. This study intends to measure the effect of work environment on employee performance in Ibom Air, Uyo, Akwa Ibom state and in particular to identify the influence of physical work environment, psychosocial work environment, technological work environment, and cultural work environment on employee performance in Ibom Air, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

- i) To what extent does the physical work environment affect employee performance in Ibom Air, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State?
- ii) What effect does psychosocial work environment have on employee performance in Ibom Air, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State?
- iii) How does the technological work environment affect employee performance in Ibom Air, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State?
- iv) To what extent does the cultural work environment affect employee performance in Ibom Air, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State?

Objective of the Study

The main Objective of the study is to examine the effect of work environment on employee performance in Ibom Air, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. While, the specific objectives are to:

- i) Ascertain the effect of physical work environment on employee performance in Ibom

Air Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

- ii) Determine the effect of psychosocial work environment on employee performance in Ibom Air Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
- iii) Evaluate the effect of technological work environment on employee performance in Ibom Air, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
- iv) Examine the effect of cultural work environment on employee performance in Ibom Air, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Research Hypotheses

The following research questions will be used to guide the study:

- HO₁: Physical work environment has no significant effect on employee performance in Ibom Air, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
- HO₂: Psychosocial work environment has no significant effect on employee performance in Ibom Air, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
- HO₃: Technological work environment has no significant effect on employee performance in Ibom Air, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
- HO₄: Cultural work environment has no significant effect on employee performance in Ibom Air, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

The goal of this chapter is to review academic literature and offer a conceptual and theoretical foundation for the variables suggested for this study. Empirical review is also covered. The chapter points out areas where the literature on the subject is lacking

Conceptual Review

In this section of the study, relevant concepts on

work environment and employee's performance and their sub- variables are reviewed.

The Concept of Work Environment

Sedarmaryati (2011) defined work environment as consisting of all tools and materials available in a work office space that enable an employee to effectively execute their function and duties with the available work system. Taiwo (2010) is of the view that work environment is the totality of interconnection that exist amid staff and also environs where they operate. It also comprises the entirety of power, undertakings and alternative prominent factors that influences the competitiveness of employees' performance.

A number of physical locations, the immediate surroundings, behavioral practices, policies, norms, culture, resources and working relationships all play a role in the workplace environment and have an impact on how workplace employees carry out their duties (Osazevaru & Amawhe, 2021). Duru and Shimawua (2017) also explains that the work environment comprises of the building, its fittings and setup as well as the physical state by which employees operate that has a constructive or defeatist impact on the mental well-being of the workers. Barry and Heizer (2001) are of the view that work environment is the physical work layout that influences employees' output, security and quality. They further state that the activities of workers are optimal when they enjoy their time working and have good interdependence between co-workers, subordinates and superiors (Surharno, et al, 2016).

Physical Work Environment

The physical work environment has been described as the most vital factor that keeps the employee going and satisfied in an organization (Niemela et al., 2002). The physical work environment comprises both internal and external office layout. Work environment is likely to affect the employee performance either negatively or positively. The workplace covers the environment in which workers carry out their work. Selecting the appropriate furniture is an important decision that must be made by managers, because it is necessary to ensure an ergonomic environment that is properly maintained with adjustable desks and chairs which can aid workers in execution of their task in a comfortable manner, since the workspace layout encourages workers to operate in line with the construction of their workstations (Jaiswal et al, 2020).

The office buildings are planned with air cooling systems, so that the thermal climate is constant at all times. Establishing the proper temperature level can also be influenced by the body mass of its employees, corpulent workers function better with lower temperature and svelte workers perform better at high temperature. The air demeanor of the work environment also contains four factors- climate, humidity, ventilation and sanitation (Manu, 2015).

Workers are able to generate their work in an environment that is properly clean, with the proper range of atmosphere conditions, adequate ventilation and ample humidity. A cozy office space must have adequate air flow that is well

circulated with electric fan, with temperature of 170 C, 210 C, 280 C, since warmest and coolest indoor climate can affect employee performance (Manu, 2015)

Psychosocial Work Environment

The Psychosocial work Environment has to do with how humans develop and interact with their surroundings. It deals with interactions with all the components of the entire work conditions. It consists of factors such as aspects of the job and work environment which include organizational climate and culture, work roles, interpersonal relationships at work and the designs and content of tasks (Bragg & Bowling 2018). A bad psychosocial work environment that has not been amended may result in some negative outcomes like bullying, suffering for employees, mental illness, stress which may affect employee performance negatively. A positive psychosocial forces have a significant impact on an employee error rate levels, efficiency and inventiveness, collaboration with coworkers, absenteeism and retention (Raos-Villagrassa, et al 2019).

Again, positive psychosocial factor can act as health - maintaining and health- enhancing agents for the employees (Bragg & Bowling 2018). As much as employees are different in their thoughts, certain work conditions are likely to be experienced differently. In order to have a psychosocial work environment that will bring positive employee performance, there is a need for managers to ensure that the following takes place. When employees are on good terms with each other and tend to appreciate team

member's effort, then there will be a positive performance in the work environment. Absence of close relationships and no appreciation of each team member will result in a negative effect on employee performance (Chen et al., 2009).

Technological Work Environment

The technological work environment consists of the tools and resources that employees use to carry out their work. Examples are mobile phones, laptops or desktop computers along with e- learning tools and software applications (Davenport & Bean, 2017). The implementation of technology in the workplace can help improve working and living conditions and can also cause a great deal of anxiety and stress among employees (Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2019).

No organization will function perfectly without the help of technology as technology helps in keeping the business well organized (Mc Clure, 2018). Some technological tools like software for management helps in building, delegating, reviewing and task assessment. With the help of technology, employees will be able to perform their task effectively while managers and employees will find it very easy to supervise workplace activities. Technology is what brings about innovation (Davenport & Bean, 2017).

A creative employee will do better with the help of technology as it will enable the employee to come up with better ideas to design products, connect with customers, market the product and this will result in better employee performance. The new trend of technology has improved employee's communication skills and allows

them to collaborate and perform efficiently. Nowadays, due to the technology in the work environment, co-workers and other members of the organization can communicate and work effectively without getting to see each other face to face (Welfare et al., 2019).

Cultural Work Environment

Culture is the identity, character, and personality of the organization. Culture is what brings about the uniqueness of the organization. No two companies can have the same goal or value proposition, in other words, no two cultures are the same. A positive cultural work environment is one that is curled out of the business mission, vision, core values and it is sustainable by what the employee puts in which is the employee's input, shifting priorities which brings about the outcome which is the performance (Aditya, Paulus & Maria, 2015).

The culture speaks volume of the organization's mission, values and ideals. The cultural work environment will either have a positive or negative effect on employee performance. As long as employees want to feel connected to each other at work, a cultural work play has a vital role to play. When employees are being attracted and retained due to the positive culture of the work environment, the employees will quickly connect with the overall business and the unique role within the organization. For a strong culture to be cultivated at the work environment, it therefore means the community will have to buy more into the values in which the culture is built on. When leaders are living the company's values,

employees are encouraged to take on their duties. The culture of work environment inspires employees to be productive and positive as this reduces employee turnover (Aditya, et al 2015)..

Employee Performance

Employee performance outlines the assigned specific and functional tasks of workers in-line with the expectations of the organization. Pattanayak (2005) proposes that the overall employee performance is as a consequence of the behavior of an employee towards the accomplishment of organization intent. Often, workers' output is synonymous to the effectiveness of leadership that may be accessed through employee performance. Thus, the primary purpose of every organization was in reviving the work overall performance of its employees by motivation through the combined efforts, abilities and perception of tasks.

Several factors have been identified toward successful employee accomplishment, physical terrain, apparatus availability, substantial work, performance expectations, assessment on accomplishment, apocalyptic plan among others (Kidane, 2022). Organizations are experiencing transformations and subsisting with the evolving needs of the environment by transcending in the business and instituting flexible aptitude for managing changes.

Business sustenance depends on the capacity, ingenuity, expertise and professionalism of employees on their performance. Performance is the accomplishment of an assigned task measured against preset known standards of

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accuracy, completeness, cost and speed and employee's performance can only be replicated through acceptable levels of precision, extensiveness, cost and speed for the achievement of the organization's objectives.

Performance is the amount of work produced in a given period of time (Alfes, et al 2010). Similarly, performance can be contingent on the accomplishment of precise task in contrast to pre-established or recognized standards of accuracy, comprehensiveness, cost and swiftness, while employment performance is adjudged to be the attainment of a commitment in such a fashion that extricate the performer from all culpabilities affirmed in their contract of employment.

Theoretical Framework

There are many theories related to the variables under study. But for the purpose of this study, the Affective Event Theory was adopted as the framework for this study. Howard, Weiss and Russel Cropanzano in 1996 propounded the affective event theory (AET) to explain the connections connecting workers' internal forces and their responses to occurrence in the work environment as it influences their output (Awoke, 2019). The tenets of the AET at workplace events are the cognitive and behavioral responses that are triggered by

employees as they operate within certain conditions that are effective in the internal workplace as it affects their performance (Kitila, 2017).

Ashton-James and Ashkanasy (2005) study sustain the postulation of AET that workplace activities do occur that prompt effective feedback from workers and that these non-cognitive responses influence workplace apprehension and behavior. Most important is the multidimensional workspace structure, physical environment and leadership system that can trigger emotional and psychological and behavioral reactions and responses among employees.

The general environment of an organization can influence certain work events, which in-turn influences employees' behaviors, thus affecting their moods, emotions and judgment when performing certain tasks, roles, duties and responsibilities. Such behavior could concomitantly influence the perceived health and welfare of the employees. Team efforts, employees motivation, physical fitness, stress and nervous exhaustion, job satisfaction, compensation, improved work performances, open plan office are a variety of work and organizational related studies that this theory has been applied to (Obulor, 2021)

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 showing Conceptual Framework of the study

Source: Researcher's conceptualization, 2024.

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Empirical Review

Published articles related the variables in this study were reviewed. The review is as follows.

Nyoman et al. (2023) conducted a study on the effect of Competence, Work Experience, Work Environment and Work Discipline on Employee Performance. The sampling method used was the census method with a total sample of 46 people. Data collection used was the method of observation, interviews and questionnaires. The collected data was processed in several stages. The descriptive analysis, multiple linear analyses. The results showed that partially the competence variable had no significant effect on employee performance. Work experience variable had no significant effect on employee performance. The work discipline variable has no significant effect on employee performance. Simultaneously, all the variables used in the study had no significant effect on performance.

Enclang-Sugiarti (2022) conducted a study on the Influence of Training, Work Environment and Career Development on Work Motivation that has an Impact on Employee Performance at PT.. The method used was a questionnaire. The sampling technique used was saturated sampling which amounted to 127 respondents. Data Analysis used were validity test, reliability test, classical assumption test, regression analysis, correlation coefficient analysis, coefficient of determination analysis and hypothesis testing. The results of the training research had a significant effect on work motivation by 31.0% and hypothesis testing was

obtained. The result also showed that work motivation had a significant effect on employee performance by 36.4%.

Elok et al., (2019) conducted a study on the effect of psychosocial work environment on employee performance through work discipline. The purpose of the study was to find out (1) the influence of the psychosocial work environment on employee performance (2) the influence of the work environment on work discipline (3) work discipline mediates the influence of the work environment on employee performance. The research adopted a quantitative approach and a proportional random sampling as a sampling technique. The population of the study amounted to 208 employees with a sample of 137 respondents from PT. GatraMapan. The result of this study showed that work discipline is able to mediate the influence of the work environment on employee performance.

Gunabeelan and Ollukkaran (2012) conducted a study on the impact of work environment on employee performance. The study showed that the work environment has a significant impact on employee performance. The respondents surveyed were the employees of the manufacturing companies. The total number of employees surveyed was 100. The study revealed how the work environment in the organization affects the employee performance. Iqra et al (2019) carried out a study on impact of technological workplace environment on employee performance/ Mediating Role of Employee Health. The study is to explore the

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impact of workplace environment i.e physical environment factors and behavioral environment factors on employee productivity (EP) through mediating role on employee health (EH). The study adopted a questionnaire survey method and data collected was from 250 employees working software houses in Pakistan. The result of the study revealed that employee health is mediating the relationship between workplace environment factors and employee performance.

Syutrika & Vergie (2016) conducted a research on the impact of the physical work environment towards employee performance at PT. Bank Negara Indonesia Manado Regional office. The research sought to understand the influence of the physical work environment on employee performance. The population used for this research is the employees of PT. Bank Negara Indonesia Mangado Regional Office with a sample size of 29 respondents. The data analysis was simple linear regression analysis, and the instrument of data collection was structured questionnaires for the top-level managers and lower-level employees. The research concluded that there is a significant effect of the physical work environment on employee performance.

Badrianto & Ekhsan (2020) conducted a study on Effect of Work Environment and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance in PT Nesinak Industries. The purpose of the study is to find out whether there is an influence of the work environment and Job satisfaction variables on employees. The sample in this

study amounted to 83 respondents who worked in the production department. The research used quantitative methods. The study used multiple linear regression analysis methods. The study showed that the variable of work environment and job satisfaction brings a positive and significant effect on employee performance partially and simultaneously.

Ravi (2017) conducted a study on the influence of cultural workplace environment on the health of leather workers in Siripuram, India involved a cross-sectional analysis with a formal interview and pretested questionnaire was administered to 230 employees, who were staff of eight different leather industries. The gathered data from the sampled population was analyzed through cluster sampling methods. The results revealed that the workplace environment has an influence on the health welfare of workers and the organizations must provide adequate facilities and conducive facilities to improve the health status of workers.

Existing Gaps for the Study

Previous research has made efforts to identify the relationship between Work environment and employees' performance in different organizations but without reference to the Airline Industry especially in developing countries like Nigeria. This study therefore proposes to fill these pertinent gaps in literature by studying the effect of work environment on employees' performance in the airline industry, particularly in Ibom Air, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Deriving knowledge in this field of study would enable stakeholders and management in the

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sector to understand and create an enabling workstation that can boost employee performance.

METHODOLOGY

The study was quantitative in approach and made use of descriptive survey design. As a result, this study employed both primary and secondary sources of data collection; the primary data were obtained from the employees through the administered questionnaire. The researcher also dropped in at the organization under study to make some personal observations just to add more credibility to the data obtained while also reducing incidence of bias or subjective views about the primary subject under investigation. Secondary data was collected through the evaluation of relevant literature. The appropriate literature was derived from books, articles, and magazines. These were sourced from E- Library at Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, and Akwa Ibom State

Population Contribution and Sample size for the study

S/N	Departments	Population Contribution	Sample size as (Gale, et al., 2018)
1.	Human resources	35	20
2.	Operations	135	276
3.	Finance	38	21
4.	Engineering	40	23
5.	Maintenance	55	31
	Total	303	471

Figure 1 showing Population Contribution for the study

University and the internet.

The primary data was gathered by the use of self-structured questionnaires titled: “Work Environment and Employee Performance Questionnaire (WEEQ). The reason for using the questionnaire survey was simply to enable the respondents to have a relaxed mind and enough time to give out the correct information. The WEEQ had three sections (A, B and C). The section A of the questionnaire was used to obtain demographic information while section B and C had 30 items on the variables under study. These items were structured on the modified five (5) point Likert Response Scale ranging from Extremely Agree (EA), to Extremely Disagree (ED).

Population this study comprise of three hundred (303) staff of Ibom Air at Akwa Ibom State. This record was obtained from the Human Resource Management Department of Ibom Air, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State as at November, 2024.

Source: HRM Ibom Air, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, 2024.

The Sample size of the study was determined with the Taro Yamene formula at 95% level of confidence and 5% margin of error (Gale, et al., 2018)

The Taro Yamene formula is given as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where: N is the Population = 303; 1 is the constant = 1; e is the degree of error expected = (0.05)²

n = 171
Data gathered were analyzed with descriptive statistics, while the hypotheses postulated were tested with multiple through the use of statistical

packages for social sciences (SPSS) version 25 software.

To ensure validity and reliability of the research instrument, the questionnaire items and its dimensions were scrutinized and modified by professionals in the field of business management. Also, a pilot study was conducted with thirty (30) employees of Ibom Air. Their response and that of experts validated the questionnaire items before distributing to respondents. The reliability of the research instrument was tested with the Cronbach's alpha through the application of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 software. The reliability coefficient of .89 was obtained. The Cronbach alpha for each construct was greater than .70 which means that the instrument was reliable and suitable for the study (Cronbach, 1951). The result of the Reliability test is shown in table 4.0 below:

Table 4.0 showing Reliability Analysis

Variables	Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Employee Performance	10	0.58
Physical Environment	6	0.57
Psychosocial Environment	6	0.61
Technological Environment	5	0.74
Cultural Environment	7	0.63

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the data analysis and hypotheses testing in accordance with the research questions and hypotheses.

Response Rate

Table 4.1: Response Rate

	Distributed Questionnaires	Retrieved Questionnaires	Unreturned Questionnaires
Frequency	171	162	9
Percentage	100%	94.7%	5.3%

Source: Researchers effort, 2024.

From table 4.1, the researcher distributed 171 questionnaires; however, it was only 162 questionnaires that were successfully retrieved. While, 9 questionnaires were not returned by the respondents..

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics was analyzed to determine mean and standard deviation of variables.

Mean and Standard Deviation

Measure of central tendency and dispersion are adopted by the study, in order determine mean – average score and standard deviation – variability index among variables. As in table 4.2, all the independent variables and dependent variable have average score of 4. On the other hand, variability index for all the independent and dependent variables falls in between 0.2 and 0.4, which means that no much difference among the response of the respondents.

Table 4.2: Mean and Standard Deviation

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation
Employee Performance	4.2204	.27146
Physical Environment	4.2290	.40974

Psychosocial Environment	4.1372	.37253
Technological Environment	4.3905	.32716
Cultural Environment	4.2255	.32028

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2024.

Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis is done using Pearson Product Correlation in order to test association between research variables. The result in Table 4.3 showed that physical environment, psychosocial environment and cultural environment have positive significant association with employee performance $r = .578$, $p < 0.01$, $r = .118$, $p < 0.05$ and $r = .121$, $p < 0.05$. On the other hand, result showed technological environment has no significant association with employee performance $r = -.002$, $p > 0.01$.

Table 4.3: Correlation Coefficient

Variables	EP	JT	JD	JS	JE
Employee Performance	1				
Physical Environment	.578**	1			
Psychosocial Environment	.118	.099	1		
Technological Environment	-.002	-.021	.262**	1	
Cultural Environment	.121	.018	-.098	-.002	1

**Correlation is significant at less than 0.01,

*Correlation is significant at less than 0.05.

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2024.

Hypotheses Testing

The result in Table 4.4 indicated the values of R-calculated (strength of relationship) and R2

(coefficient of determination of the extent of effect) of physical environment, psychosocial environment, technological environment and cultural environment on employee performance in Ibom Air is R-value of 0.35; indicated that physical work environment, psychosocial environment, technological environment and cultural environment affects employee performance in Ibom Air.

Table 4.4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				Durbin-Watson	
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2		Sig. F Change
1	.593 ^a	.351	.333	.22171	.351	19.218	4	42	.000	2.023

a. Predictors: (Constant), Cultural Environment, Technological Environment, Physical Environment, Psychosocial Environment

b. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance
Also, the result of ANOVA indicated the values of regression residual, mean square and F value showed that the effect of physical environment, psychosocial environment, technological environment and cultural environment on employee performance in Ibom Air, are highly significant at less than 0.01.

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
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Regression	3.779	4	.945	19.218	.000 ^b
Residual	6.980	142	.049		
Total	10.759	146			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Cultural Environment, Technological Environment, Physical Environment, Psychosocial Environment

Additionally, Table 4.4 indicated the findings of the null hypotheses tested. According to results, Hypothesis 1 which states physical work environment has no significant effect on employee performance was not supported, because the B = .376, t-value = 8.345 and p-value = .000 showed that physical environment has significant effect on employee performance at less than 0.01 significance level. Thus, the hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted.

On the contrary, regression result of Hypothesis 2 which states that psychosocial work environment has no significant effect on employee performance is statistically supported, as the B = .055, t-value = 1.067 and p-value = .288 showed that physical environment has no significant effect on employee performance even at less than 0.1 significance level. Thus, the hypothesis is accepted and alternate hypothesis is rejected.

Similarly, regression result of Hypothesis 3 which states that technological work environment has no significant effect on employee performance is statistically supported, as the B = -.008, t-value = -.143 and p-value = .886 showed that technological environment has no significant effect on employee performance even at less than 0.1 significance level. Thus, the hypothesis is accepted and alternate hypothesis is rejected.

However, regression result of Hypothesis 4 which states cultural work environment has no significant effect on employee performance was not supported, because the B = .100, t-value = 1.744 and p-value = .083 showed that cultural environment has significant effect on employee performance at less than 0.01 significance level.

Thus, the hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Table 4.5: Hypotheses Testing

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Decision
	B	Std. Error				
(Constant)	2.014	.422		4.767	.000	
Physical Environment	.376	.045	.568	8.345	.000	Rejected
Psychosocial Environment	.055	.052	.076	1.067	.288	Accepted
Technological Environment	-.008	.058	-.010	-.143	.886	Accepted
Cultural Environment	.100	.058	.119	1.744	.083	Rejected

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study are presented according to the research questions answered and the null hypotheses tested in the subheadings.

Physical work environment and Employee performance

The result of hypothesis one revealed that, Physical work environment has a significant effect on employee performance. This finding could be attributed to factors such as workspace layout, lighting and ventilation, ergonomics, Noise level and safety and security. The layout of the workspace should be designed to facilitate collaboration, communication, and efficient workflow. It should provide adequate space for

employees to perform their tasks comfortably and with ease. In addition, a well-organized workspace can reduce clutter and distractions, enabling employees to focus better on their work. The result showed that physical environment comfort factors have significant impact on employee's health which indirectly affects their absenteeism rate. The finding of this study also agreed with the study done by Anto & Gunaselan (2012) on "the impact of work environment on employee performance". The finding revealed that a work environment has a significant impact on employee performance and productivity.

Psychosocial work environment and Employee performance

The result of hypothesis two revealed that, psychosocial work environment has no significant effect on employee performance. This finding could be attributed to factors such as leadership Style, teamwork and collaboration, job satisfaction, work-life balance and social support. Effective leadership is crucial in shaping the psychosocial work environment. Leaders who provide clear direction, support employee development, and encourage collaboration can inspire higher levels of performance. On the other hand, autocratic or unsupportive leadership styles can lead to low morale, decreased motivation, and reduced productivity. The result showed that employees' motivation on employees' performance in parastatals can be influenced with the work environment itself. The finding of this study also agreed with the study done by Elok et al., (2019) on "the influence of psychosocial work environment on employee

performance". The finding revealed that there is a significant influence of the psychosocial work environment on employee performance.

Technological work environment and Employee performance

The result of hypothesis three revealed that, Technological work environment has no significant effect on employee performance. This finding could be attributed to the fact that as an airline, Ibom Air relies heavily on technology for various aspects of its operations. Here's how the technological work environment can affect employee performance: A technologically advanced work environment can streamline processes and enhance operational efficiency. Providing employees with up-to-date software, hardware, and digital tools can simplify tasks, automate repetitive processes, and reduce manual errors.

This improves productivity, allowing employees to accomplish tasks more efficiently and focus on higher-value activities. In addition, Technology enables effective collaboration and communication among team members, regardless of their physical location. Platforms such as project management software, instant messaging, video conferencing, and email facilitate seamless information sharing, real-time collaboration, and efficient decision-making.

This connectivity helps employees work together effectively, improving coordination and overall performance. Technology provides quick and easy access to information, databases, and

resources that employees need to perform their jobs. With the right systems in place, employees can access relevant data, reports, and documentation promptly, enabling them to make informed decisions and carry out their responsibilities more effectively. This access to information enhances employee performance and customer service quality.

Cultural Work Environment and Employee performance

The result of hypothesis four revealed that, Cultural work environment has a significant effect on employee performance. This finding could be attributed to factors such as diversity and inclusion, recognition and rewards, and employee engagement. A culturally diverse and inclusive work environment positively affects employee performance. When employees feel that their diverse perspectives, experiences, and backgrounds are respected and valued, they are more likely to contribute their unique insights and ideas.

A culture that embraces diversity and inclusion fosters creativity, innovation, and better decision-making, leading to improved performance. In addition, a culture that recognizes and rewards employee contributions enhances performance. When employees are acknowledged for their achievements, efforts, and contributions, it boosts motivation, job satisfaction, and loyalty. A culture of recognition creates a positive work environment where employees feel appreciated and valued, leading to increased productivity and performance.

Finally, a positive cultural work environment fosters employee engagement.

Conclusion

The principal purpose of this research was to empirically investigate the effect of work environment on employee performance. Employee attitude, behavior, concentration, satisfaction and performance are likely to improve when they operate in an ideal physical, technological, psychosocial, and cultural work environment. Employers must therefore take into consideration the physical office layout, sound, lighting, color, interactions among employees and other factors that affect employee performance.

Based on the findings that work environment factors such as physical work environment, psychosocial work environment, technological work environment and cultural work environment significantly affect employee performance in Ibom Air, Uyo. Ibom Air staff are bound to have job commitment and work towards attainment of organizational goals if their concerns for the work environment are known and addressed. On the part of organizations, there is need for them to upgrade their work environments and structures by inculcating modernized, comfortable structures that can bring positive outcomes and performance of employees.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

- 1) Ibom Air management should always provide physical work environment that involves workspace layout, safety and security since it

enhances employee performance.

2) Ibom Air management should always provide psychosocial work environment that involves effective leadership style, work-life balance, teamwork and collaboration, social support since it enhances employee performance.

3) Ibom Air management should always provide technological work environment that involves efficiency and productivity, access to information, data analysis and decision-making resources since it enhances employee performance.

4) Ibom Air management should always provide cultural work environment that involves diversity and inclusion, and recognition and rewards since it enhances employee performance.

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